

Occupational Health Safety Practices and Employee Performance in Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State

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Accepted: March 26th, 2022

Published: March 31st, 2022

Citations - APA

Okechukwu, Elizabeth Uzoamaka and Onyia, Angela Chizoba (2022). Occupational Health Safety Practices and Employee Performance in Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State. *Contemporary Journal of Management*, 4(2), 1-13.

The study was carried out to examine the relationship between occupational health safety practices and employee performance in manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives include: Evaluate the relationship between safety planning and output of manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria, and investigate the relationship between training programme and quality of service in manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. The target population of this study consists of senior and junior staff of the selected food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Out of a population of two thousand, five hundred and fifty-four (2,554) staff, the sample size of 486 was chosen after applying the Bill Godden (2004) formula for the determination of an adequate sample size. Three hundred and ninety-two (392) returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to assess the reliability (r). It also yielded a good reliability coefficient of 0.84. Regression analysis was used to examine the data. The findings revealed that there is a positive significant relationship. In Enugu State, Nigeria, there is a link between safety planning and manufacturing output. There was a positive significant relationship between training program and quality of service in manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria, $r(95, n=486) = 427.877, P0.05, r(95, n=486) = 575.996, P0.05$. According to the findings, safety planning and training programs had a positive impact on the output and service quality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Nigeria's Enugu state. As a result, the study recommended that management provide regular education and training on occupational health and safety issues in order to prevent workplace injuries and thus increase productivity.

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ABSTRACT

Keywords: Occupational Health Safety Practices; Employee Performance; Manufacturing Firms; Enugu State

1. Introduction

Aside from their homes, the workplace is where many people spend the majority of their time. Indeed, for the majority of people, especially in developing countries like Nigeria, the line between home and workplace is blurred because they engage in agricultural or cottage industry activities at home. Work contributes to good health and economic success in favorable circumstances. However, many workers are exposed to health hazards at work, which can lead to injuries and systemic disorders such as respiratory, cardiovascular, reproductive, and nervous system disorders. Occupational morbidity, disability, and mortality are becoming a serious public health problem in most developing countries, including Nigeria, and are posing challenges to achieving the millennium development goals of poverty reduction and universal health coverage. In the developing world's manufacturing industries, evidence-based occupational health and safety services are critical. (Asikhia and Emenike, 2013). Humanity's inability to fit its activities into that pattern is changing planetary systems, fundamentally. Many of these changes come with life-threatening risks. This new reality, from which there is no getting away, must be acknowledged - and managed (From One Earth) (Rebecca, 2013).

Organizations with employees who are at high risk of getting injured, often have structured and well-designed occupational safety strategies in place. They understand that having a good plan can significantly improve employees' health, safety, and wellbeing because they are aware of the consequences of ignoring workplace safety (Martic, 2020). Employee performance is determined by factors such as work quality, quantity, and effectiveness, as well as how your employees behave in the workplace (Ashley and Thompson, 2019). Understanding performance metrics, employee performance review methods, and ways to improve performance will assist organizations in ensuring that their workforce is capable of meeting the needs of the company and its customers. Employees are drawn to a workplace that is free of accidents and injuries. Employees are more content and productive in such an environment. Employees and employers both want to work in a safe environment. All employees have the right to work in a safe environment.

Occupational health and safety (OHS) is a multidisciplinary field concerned with the safety, health, and welfare of people at work. The goal of an occupational safety and health program is to promote a safe and healthy working environment. Co-workers, family members, employers, customers, and others who may be affected by the workplace environment may be protected by OHS (Fanning, 2013). The primary goal of workplace security and well-being programs is to stop factory injuries, sicknesses, and possible deaths, as well as the suffering and financial adversity that these actions can cause for employees, their families, and employers, while also improving their performance. The study is therefore carried out to examine the relationship between occupational health safety practices and employee performance in manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

Occupational health and safety regulations require the removal, reduction, or replacement of hazards on the job site. The use of mitigating factors to either reduce or eliminate active risks and hazards, as well as the establishment of a workplace that minimizes active risks and hazards, was encouraged. In Nigeria, safe and healthy workplaces are frequently taken for granted. Improving a company's occupational health and safety standards ensures good business, a better brand image, and higher employee morale.

The workforce's attitude toward safety practices is uninspiring, and one wonders if safety principles even exist in their heads when they're at work. It is unnecessary to emphasize the fact that we see artisans every day in public spaces such as manufacturing plant floors, construction sites, road repair sites, and even mechanic shops and workers not properly dressed for their jobs, which demonstrates the level of disregard for safety culture among Nigerian workers. Occupational health services are supposed to play an important role in the prevention, control, and rehabilitation of occupational diseases and injuries.

Failure to tackle the challenges of occupational health and safety management system at work places might lead to poor performance of the firms as a result of poor quality of service, low output etc. These effects might have been caused either directly by exposure to safety hazards and harmful agents. The study therefore, examines the relationship between occupational health safety practices and employee performance in manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine occupational health safety practices and employee performance in manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives include:

- i. Evaluate the relationship between safety planning and output of manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.
- ii. Investigate the relationship between training programme and quality of service in manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study:

- i. There is no significant relationship between safety planning and output of manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between training programme and quality of service in manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Occupational Health and Safety

Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) relates to health, safety, and welfare issues in the workplace. OHS refers to the laws, regulations, and programs aimed at improving the working environment for employees, as well as coworkers, family members, customers, and other stakeholders. The single most important factor in reducing accidents is to establish a strong health and safety culture in the workplace. While the health and safety challenges may change in the future, as the ILO's recent report indicates, the need to cut costs, keep workers healthy, and reduce company risks remains constant (Sikra, 2019). The Occupational Health and Safety Administration, state affiliated agencies, national agencies, and international agencies may all impose health and safety regulations. Private industry and trade associations can also set voluntary requirements and monitor their employer members' compliance. Finally, if an employer fails to follow the rules, he or she may face a fine or be ordered to stop working. It's also possible that the employer's industry or trade group will take action against him (Janalta, 2021). Workplaces designed according to good occupational health, safety, and ergonomics principles are also the most sustainable and productive, as demonstrated by the most successful economies. Furthermore, in poor working conditions with workers who are exposed to health and safety risks, a healthy economy, high-quality products or services, and long-term productivity are difficult to achieve, hazards, according to extensive experience from countries.

The value of several principles is demonstrated by available scientific knowledge and practical experiences of enterprises and countries that have achieved the best results in the development of occupational health. These principles have been found to be common denominators in workplaces that have produced the best results in terms of health, safety, social relations, and economic success. In times of crisis, businesses with such occupational settings are the most stable. Adequate legal provisions, administrative enforcement, and service systems for occupational safety and health and occupational health services are required for the implementation of such principles.

Employee Performance

One of the most important factors affecting an organization's performance is employee performance. HR is a critical factor that has a direct impact on and contributes to the performance of a successful organization (AL-Qudah, Osman, Halim & Al-Shatanawi, 2014). The success of any organization depends on its employees behaviour and their decision, although there are many other factors that contribute to the success, such as the organization size, the environment in what it operate and its activities. Human resource management practices are frequently used to evaluate an employee's performance in the workplace, and in today's highly competitive environment, the tendency to improve employee performance is to improve HRM practices (Caliskan, 2010; Bowra, Sharif, Saeed, & Niazi, 2012). The employee's performance is use of knowledge, skills, experiences and abilities, to perform the assigned mission

required by their managers efficiently and effectively. The importance of employee performance can be expressed in a variety of ways, including 1) assisting in the costing of resources used, 2) a measure of the quantity and quality of work completed, 3) assisting in the survival and excelling of firms, 4) assisting in the assessment and attainment of established performance goals, and finally, 5) increasing the efficiency of employee performance aids in making the best decisions.

Hamzah, Abdullah, and Hamzah (2014) explained how to evaluate employee performance using the following criteria: 1) employee attributes, which confirm important characteristics or qualities to the firm; 2) employee behaviors, which are widely used for evaluating or defining employee behaviors required to complete a job successfully; and 3) employee achievements, which demonstrate the extent to which specific objectives or aims have been met, exceeded, or not met. (Hamzah et al., 2014). Employee performance does not have a single, overarching theory. The efficiency with which organizations manage, develop, and motivate their employees is a critical factor in how well they perform. People management has a significant impact on performance as a result of this. The behavior of people on the shop floor can be traced back to performance (Lodewijk, 2017).

Safety Planning

Safety planning entails thinking of ways to stay safe while also reducing the risk of future harm. It may entail preparing for a future crisis, weighing your options, and deciding on your next course of action. Finding ways to stay and feel safer can be a big step toward recovery, but these plans and actions shouldn't put you in danger (Rainn, 2021). Every employer must pay attention to their employees' health as well as the safety and security of the environment in which they work. It could be their home, workplace, or any other location where they live. For employees to live a happy life, their surroundings must be clean, hygienic, safe, and secure.

We certainly take care of our surroundings when we are at home, but what about at work? This is a significant question that everyone should consider. We spend more time in the office or at work than we do at home during our peak hours. As a result, it is critical to be safe and healthy at work. As a result, workplace safety is one of the most critical aspects of any business. As an employer, you should provide a safe working environment for your employees, keeping their health and safety in mind. Investing in workplace safety is always prudent-especially when you consider the high cost of injury for both the employer and the individual worker (Sundberg, 2018).

Training Programme

In the field of human resource development, training is a fundamental concept. It is concerned with teaching and practicing a particular skill to a desired standard. Training is a powerful tool for putting an employee in a position where they can do their job correctly, efficiently, and with integrity. Training is the process of improving an employee's knowledge and skills in order for them to perform a specific job (Smriti, 2021). The prime motivator for employee training is to improve productivity and performance. And when executed well, it does just that. This course aims to provide participants with the fundamental knowledge and skills needed to identify safety, health, and environmental hazards, as well as develop and implement OSH policies and programs (O'Neill, 2020). Safety training refers to educational programs that teach employees how to use preventative processes and procedures to reduce the risk of injury or death on the job. Safety training is a type of compliance training that is given to keep the company and its employees safe.

Output

Output, according to Business Dictionary (2019) refers to the amount of energy, work, goods, or services produced by a machine, factory, company, or an individual in a period. It could also be referred to as the desired result from a project or contractor. In the case of services, the concept of an output is less straightforward than in the case of physical goods. Because the majority of publicly produced outputs are services rather than goods, this is especially important in the public sector. There is no physical object that constitutes the output in the case of services. The service provider intervenes directly with a client or subject in order to effect change in that client or subject. This allows the client/subject to have a direct role in the production process, which is not possible with goods. Because of these distinguishing characteristics of services, it's always been difficult to tell the difference between outputs

and outcomes, and outputs and activities (Robinson, 2003). Typically, outputs are in contemporary defined as “the products and services produced by a program or activity” (World Bank 1998).

Quality of Service

Organizations have realized that service quality brings a sustainable and competitive advantage. Service quality is a comparison of customer expectations with service performance. High-quality service organizations meet customer needs while also remaining the most cost-effective in terms of competition, as improved service quality makes a company more competitive. High service quality is achieved by understanding operational processes, identifying service problems, and defining service performance and outcome measures, as well as customer satisfaction levels (Borgave, 2016). Service quality refers to a service provider's ability to satisfy customers in a timely and efficient manner so that he can improve business performance. 'Quality' is a critical component of business success in the service sector as well. It is because of the realization of its positive link with profits, increased market share, customer satisfaction (Ramya, Kowsalya and Dharanipriya, 2019).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by Protection Motivation Theory (PMT).

Protection Motivation Theory (PMT)

The Protection Motivation Theory was used as a foundation for the research (PMT). Rogers (1975) proposed Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) to provide conceptual clarity to the understanding of fear appeals. Rogers (1983) revised Protection Motivation Theory to become a more general theory of persuasive communication, with a focus on the cognitive processes that mediate behavioral change. Protection Motivation Theory (Rogers, 1983) describes adaptive and maladaptive coping with a health threat as a result of two appraisal processes, and is based in part on Lazarus (1966) and Leventhal's research (1970). A threat assessment and coping assessment process is used to evaluate the behavioral options for reducing the threat (Boer, Seydel, 1996). The evaluation of the health threat and the evaluation of coping responses either leads to the desire to engage in adaptive responses (protection motivation) or to the intention to perform maladaptive responses (maladaptive motivation). Maladaptive responses are those that put a person's health in jeopardy. They include behaviors that have negative consequences (e.g., smoking) as well as behaviors that do not have negative consequences but may eventually do so (e.g., not participating in breast cancer screening and thus missing the opportunity of early detection of a tumor).

According to the Protection Motivation Theory, the desire to protect oneself is influenced by four factors:

1. The perceived seriousness of an impending event (e.g., a heart attack)
2. The occurrence's perceived likelihood, or vulnerability (in this example, the perceived vulnerability of the individual to a heart attack)
3. The effectiveness of the suggested preventive behavior (the perceived response efficacy)
4. Perceived self-efficacy (i.e., one's belief in one's own ability to carry out the recommended preventive behavior).

The threat and coping appraisals combine to produce protection motivation. Threat appraisal is the process of estimating the likelihood of contracting a disease (vulnerability) as well as the severity of the disease (severity). Response efficacy and self-efficacy are two components of coping appraisal. The individual's expectation that following the recommendations will eliminate the threat is referred to as response efficacy. Self-efficacy is the belief in one's ability to successfully carry out the recommended actions. Protection motivation is a mediating variable that is responsible for arousing, maintaining, and directing protective health behavior (Boer, Seydel, 1996).

The Protection Motivation Theory can be used to predict and influence a wide range of behaviors. The PMT can, of course, be used in health-related behaviors. To date, the primary goals of the application have been to reduce alcohol consumption, promote healthy lifestyles, improve diagnostic health behaviors, and prevent disease. (Stainback and Rogers, 1983) used the PMT to try to figure out how to reduce alcohol consumption. They used persuasive messages to teach junior high school students about the negative consequences of binge drinking. They divided the participants into two groups, with the high-fear group receiving messages describing severe

consequences with a high likelihood of occurrence. The low-fear group received messages stating that there would be no serious consequences and that the likelihood of occurrence was low. According to the findings of this study, the high-fear group rated the severity of the consequences and the likelihood of experiencing these consequences as being higher than the low-fear group. Immediately after exposure to the information the high-fear condition produced stronger intentions to remain abstinent than the lower-fear condition (Boer, Seydel, 1996).

2.3 Empirical Review

Wabara, Sampson and Okwudili (2017) examined the effects of manpower development on organisational efficiency, with reference to pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria; covering the period of 2014 to 2016. The specific objectives were to; identify the manpower training and developmental programmes adopted by pharmaceutical manufacturing firms Enugu State, in developing their employees, determining the impact of training and developmental programs on employee performance, and identifying challenges impeding pharmaceutical manufacturing firms' efficiency in Enugu State. The researcher used a survey research design and used both primary and secondary data. The analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics and logistic regression analysis. The findings revealed that orientation, internship training, case study method, seminar/workshop, and classroom method are the most common training and development programs used by pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State to develop their manpower, with internship training method, case study method, and seminar/workshop having an impact on employee performance. Also, findings revealed that lack of modern equipment, inadequate megawatts of power, overload networks, vandalization/militancy, government policies, peculiarities of transmission and distribution network where the major problems responsible for the poor performance and inefficiency of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. According to the researcher, training programs should be designed to familiarize individual participants with specific knowledge and skills required to improve their efficiency in the workplace while also serving the employee's career goals. The importance of the organization's manpower development policies being continuous and consistent with their strategic policies was also emphasized.

Suleiman, Amin, Ilyas, Ruth and Rasheed (2018) examined the impact of employees' training on organization profitability. 269 employees were chosen from a total population of 874 employees drawn from 10 profit-making organizations (firms and schools) in Kwara State, Nigeria, using two sampling techniques (multistage and random). To collect relevant data, the 'Training and Organization Profitability Questionnaire (TOPQ)' was adapted. Data was screened using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The psychometric properties were then assessed using partial least square (PLS) (i.e., to determine the measurement and structural model of the study). There is no link between on-the-job training and company profitability, but there is a significant link between specialized training and company profitability. It was also discovered that the variance explained in the study's exogenous model is 24%, that effect sizes for on-the-job and specialized training are none and small, respectively, and that adequate predictive relevance was achieved. The study concludes that the value of training cannot be overstated, and that business and educational leaders should provide their employees with the training they require for the organization's growth and development.

Kabiru, Theuri and Misiko (2018) conducted a study to find out how planning influenced the performance of these state corporations. The goal of this research was to look into the impact of planning on the organizational performance of Kenyan agricultural state-owned corporations. The study employed a descriptive research design. 42 agricultural state-owned corporations made up the target population. Out of Kenya's 42 agricultural state-owned corporations, a sample of 30 was chosen using a simple random sampling technique. Data was gathered through the use of questionnaires that were distributed using the 'drop and pick later method.' The questionnaire was divided into six sections and consisted of structured questions to thoroughly cover the study's goal. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences and Microsoft Excel 2007 was used to code and analyze the data using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Findings were presented in graphs charts, pie charts and tables. They stated that planning has an impact on state corporation organizational performance, but based on the data gathered, it is inferred that the management of these corporations does not perform planning functions appropriately or effectively. If these companies are to improve their performance, the study suggests that effective planning become a corporate culture.

Kharoub and Mansour (2019) investigated the impact of strategic planning in Palestinian Municipalities on the Quality of service provided to citizens. Reviewing journals, books, bulletins, textbooks, scientific articles, newspapers, periodicals, and other sources provided secondary data. A specific questionnaire was used to collect primary data. The questionnaire had 45 items in total, divided into three sections: personal information, strategic planning, and quality dimensions. One hundred and twenty (120) questionnaires were randomly distributed to Jenin Municipality employees, one hundred and fourteen (114) questionnaires were retrieved, and six cases were investigated (missing cases). In this study, the researcher used the SERVQUAL model and made some changes to it to fit the study's main goals.

To answer the study question, the researcher used an analytical descriptive approach and tested three main hypotheses that were clarified during the study. The main findings revealed that strategic planning has a positive correlation and impact on the quality of service provided to citizens, as well as the sub-hypothesis (tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, empathy, and assurance) as investigated by respondents, and this applies to all four factors (vision, mission, objectives, and strategic choices), as well as the level of satisfaction with the quality of service provided by Jenin municipality, which was measured. The researcher advised Palestinian municipalities to promote a quality culture and encourage employees to take part in hazard identification processes, creative and innovation opportunities.

3. Methodology

The study was based on examining the relationship between occupational health safety practices and employee performance in manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The researcher obtained data through the use of a questionnaire. The study used the survey approach. The primary sources was the administration of an inquiry to the management and staff of the studied firms. The senior and junior staff of the selected food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State are the study's target population. After applying the Bill, Godden (2004) formula for determining an adequate sample size, a sample size of 486 was chosen from a population of 2,554 employees. Three hundred and ninety-two is the number of people who live in the United States (392) returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability coefficient of 0.84 which was also good. The data were analyzed using regression analysis.

Sample Size – Infinite Population (where the population is greater than 50,000)

$$SS = \frac{Z^2 \times P \times (1-P)}{C^2}$$

Where:

SS = Sample Size

Z = Z-value (e.g., 1.96 for a 95 percent confidence level)

P = percentage of population picking a choice, expressed as decimal

C = Confidence interval, expressed as decimal (e.g., .04= + - 4 percentage points)

A Z-values (Cumulative Normal Probability Table) represent the probability that a sample will fall within a certain distribution.

The Z-values for confidence levels are:

1.645 = 90 percent confidence level

1.96 = 95 percent confidence level

2.576 = 99 percent confidence level

Example:

$$SS = \frac{3.8416 \times .5 \times .5}{.0016}$$

$$SS = 600$$

Sample Size –Finite Population (where the population is less than 50,000)

$$\text{New SS} = \frac{SS}{\frac{1+(SS-1)}{\text{Pop}}}$$

Pop = Population (e.g., 2554)

$$\text{New SS} = \frac{600}{\frac{1+(600-1)}{2554}}$$

$$\text{New SS} = 486.03$$

$$\text{Sample Size} = 486$$

Bill Godden, January 2004

4. Data Presentation and Analyses

4.1 Data Presentation

Research Question One: What is the relationship between safety planning and output of manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria?

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The organisation brainstorming ways to stay safe and increase earnings	392	1	5	1537	3.92	1.160
My organisation has plan for a future crisis which helps to reduce expenses	392	1	5	1584	4.04	1.048
My organisation concentrate on employees health and safety to reduce absenteeism	392	1	6	1619	4.13	.930
Effective decisions are made about our next steps to avoid failure	392	1	5	1585	4.04	1.160
Valid N (listwise)	392					

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From table one, the mean score of 3.92 and the deviation of 1.160 shows that the organisation brainstorming ways to stay safe and increase earnings, my organisation has plan for a future crisis which helps to reduce expenses with a mean score of 4.04 and standard deviation of 1.048, my organisation concentrate on employees health and safety to reduce absenteeism with a mean score of 4.13 and standard deviation of .930 and as shown by the data, the high mean score of 4.04, supports that Effective decisions are made about our next steps to avoid failure.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between training programme and quality of service in manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria?

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Training is done in the organisation when employee is promoted to another department	392	1	5	1287	3.28	.959
Employees are brought into a position where they can do their work correctly	392	1	5	1370	3.49	.873
The old employees are equipped with new techniques and technologies.	392	1	5	1600	4.08	1.146
In my organisation engaged employees have increased level of productivity through training	392	1	5	1670	4.26	.998
Valid N (listwise)	392					

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From table 4.2, with the mean score of 3.28 and the deviation of .959 showing that Training is done in the organisation when employee is promoted to another department. Employees are brought into a position where they can do their work correctly with a mean score of 3.49 and standard deviation of .873, The old employees are equipped with new techniques and technologies with a mean score of 4.08 and standard deviation of 1.146, In my organisation engaged employees have increased level of productivity through training with 4.26 mean score and .998 standard deviation.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between safety planning and output of manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.772 ^a	.596	.595	.766

a. Predictors: (Constant), TOBWSS, MOPFCW, MOCEHS, EDMAON

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	337.914	1	337.914	575.996	.000 ^b
Residual	228.798	390	.587		
Total	566.712	391			

- a. Dependent Variable: RBESPO
b. Predictors: (Constant), ECSRIOP, IRFLNIE, ARCBPIG, OCCAPDP.

Where:

RBESPO: Relationship between safety planning and output of manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria

TOBWSS: The organisation brainstorming ways to stay safe and increase earnings

Mopfcw: My organisation has plan for a future crisis which helps to reduce expenses

MOCEHS: My organisation concentrate on employee's health and safety to reduce absenteeism

EDMAON: Effective decisions are made about our next steps to avoid failure

The R² {R-Squared} which measures the overall goodness of fit of the complete regression, shows the value as .596 and adjusted to .595. This means that R² accounts for approximately 59 percent. This indicates that the independent variables account for about 59 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. Which shows a good fit as a result, the f-calculated value of 575.996 is greater than the f-tabulated value of 2.7858, indicating that f-cal > f-tab. As a result, we reject the null hypothesis H0 and accept the Alternative hypothesis, which states that the overall estimate is well-fitting, implying that our independent variables are also significant. We have now concluded that there is a positive significant relationship between safety planning and manufacturing firm output in Enugu State, Nigeria, based on our analysis.

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between training programme and quality of service in manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.724 ^a	.524	.523	.854

a. Predictors: (Constant), TDOWEP,EBPWTDW, TOEENT, IMOEEIL

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	312.059	1	312.059	427.877	.000 ^b
	Residual	282.977	388	.729		
	Total	595.036	389			

- a. Dependent Variable: RBTPQS
b. Predictors: (Constant), TDOWEP,EBPWTDW, TOEENT, IMOEEIL

Where:

RBTPQS: Relationship between training programme and quality of service in manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.

TDOWEP: Training is done in the organisation when employee is promoted to another department

EBPWTDW: Employees are brought into a position where they can do their work correctly

TOEENT: The old employees are equipped with new techniques and technologies.

IMOEEILL: In my organisation engaged employees have increased level of productivity through training

The R^2 {R-Squared} which measures the overall goodness of fit of the complete regression, shows the value as 524 and adjusted to 523. This means that R^2 accounts for approximately 52 percent. This indicates that the independent variables account for about 52 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. Which shows a good fit. The result shows that f-calculated 427.877 is greater than f-tabulated 2.7858, indicating that $f\text{-cal} > f\text{-tab}$. As a result, we reject the null hypothesis H_0 and accept the Alternative hypothesis, which states that the overall estimate is well-fitting, implying that our independent variables are also significant. We have now concluded that there is a positive significant relationship between training program and service quality in manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria, based on our analysis.

Discussion of Findings

The test of hypothesis one result showed that f-calculated {575.996} is greater than the f-tabulated {2.7858}, that is, $f\text{-cal} > f\text{-tab}$. Thus, the alternate hypothesis was accepted which states that there is positive significant relationship safety planning and output of manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. Every employer must pay attention to their employees' health as well as the safety and security of the environment in which they work. It could be their home, workplace, or any other location where they live. For employees to live a happy life, their surroundings must be clean, hygienic, safe, and secure. We spend more time in the office or at work than we do at home during our peak hours. As a result, it is critical to be safe and healthy at work. So, workplace safety is one of the very important aspects of any organization (Rainn, 2021).

In the test of hypothesis two, the result showed that f-calculated {427.877} is greater than the f-tabulated {2.7858}, that is, $f\text{-cal} > f\text{-tab}$. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. Thus, the alternate hypothesis was accepted which states that there is positive significant relationship between training programme and quality of service in manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. Adequate safety training helps employees understand the various hazards related to their job and gives them the tools they need to safeguard against those hazards. In addition to showing them how to work safely, participating in safety training allows them to better relate to their employees.

5.1 Conclusions

The study concluded that safety planning and training programmes had positive effect on the output and quality of service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. Occupational health and safety are one of the tools granted by law to encourage workers to behave in a safe manner. This is a multidisciplinary field concerned with ensuring the safety, health, and well-being of employees in the workplace. All occupational health and safety programs have the same goal: to create a safe working environment. It may also protect co-workers, adjacent communities, and other members of the public who are affected by the office environment as a secondary consequence.

5.2 Recommendations

From the findings, the following were recommended:

- i. Employees should be involved in the planning process in order to foster a quality culture and encourage participation in hazard identification as well as opportunities for creativity and innovation.
- ii. To prevent workplace injuries and thus promote productivity, management should provide regular education and training on occupational health and safety concerns.

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